

Groundbreaking research and disruption: Empirical results on the correlation between assessments of groundbreaking research by peers and disruption index scores

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Abstract

The study by Park et al. (2023), which found that disruptive innovations in science have been declining since the end of World War II, triggered a public debate about an apparent lack of major scientific achievements in the modern science system. However, could it be that not all important contributions to the progress of science are captured as “disruptive” by the metric used by Park et al. (2023)? Their metric, the disruption index, might not be suitable for identifying major scientific achievements (groundbreaking research). In this study, we tested whether the disruption index (two variants: DI_1 , DI_5) corresponds with researchers’ self-assessments of their own work as groundbreaking. The results of the study show that the researchers define groundbreaking science as research that is novel and important. Furthermore, the results reveal that the DI_1 and the DI_5 fail to identify publications that have been defined as groundbreaking science by the researchers.

1. Introduction

Given the importance of transformative research for the evolution of human knowledge, it is not surprising that a metric by the name of disruption index [originally: CD index, here: DI_1], which promises to be able to quantify and identify disruptive science, has quickly captured the attention and imagination of science of science researchers in recent years. Since the introduction of the DI_1 by Funk and Owen-Smith (2017), no less than three studies have been published in the influential *Nature* magazine using the DI_1 as a measure of transformative research (Lin et al., 2023; Park et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2019).

The findings of Park et al. (2023) have made waves in and beyond the science system because they suggest that there has been a steady decline of disruptive papers and patents in every discipline since the end of World War II. Unsurprisingly, these striking results triggered a public debate about the apparent stagnation of the global science system. Some media outlets

have interpreted it as possibly indicating a lack of “major advances” (Hart, 2023) and “real breakthroughs” (Broad, 2023) in a science system that seems to be running out of steam. However, before drawing such conclusions, we need to have clarity about concepts and measurements. Many significant contributions to scientific progress might not be disruptive as measured by the index. For example, the paper by Davis et al. (1995) about the Bose-Einstein condensation has a low DI_1 score (Wu et al., 2019), but it was deemed worthy of a Nobel Prize. In 2001, Wolfgang Ketterle received the Nobel prize (together with Eric Cornell and Carl Wieman) “for the achievement of Bose-Einstein condensation in dilute gases of alkali atoms”¹. This example shows that not all “real breakthroughs” are identified as disruptive by the index: a decline in DI_1 scores may not necessarily mean that there is a decline in major scientific achievements. It seems that the DI_1 cannot be interpreted as a measure of groundbreaking research.

This paper aims to assess whether high disruption scores are a valid indicator of groundbreaking science. To this end, we used data from a survey that asked researchers to assess quality dimensions of their own papers. In the first part of our study, we clarified how the DI_1 and its variants operationalize disruptive science and how this relates to the concept of groundbreaking research. The second part complements the conceptual work by presenting empirical evidence on how the researchers define groundbreaking research.

2. Disruption as discontinuity in citation networks

Figure 1: Calculation of the DI_1 . The illustration is based on Funk and Owen-Smith (2017)

The DI_1 is related to measures of betweenness centrality (Freeman, 1977; Gebhart & Funk, 2023) and its calculation is grounded in bibliographic coupling. The DI_1 differentiates between

¹ <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/lists/all-nobel-prizes/2009-2000/>

three types of bibliographic coupling links (see Figure 1). Papers of type R (standing for “reference”) only cite the FP’s cited references, but not the FP itself.² Paper of type B (standing for “both”) cite both the FP and at least one of the FP’s cited references. Papers of type F (standing for “focal”) cite only the focal paper and none of its cited references. The DI_1 is equivalent to the following ratio:

$$DI_1 = \frac{N_F - N_B}{N_F + N_B + N_R}$$

Bornmann et al. (2020) propose a variant of DI_1 , the DI_5 , which mitigates some of the DI_1 ’s weaknesses (especially randomness in bibliographic couplings) by only considering citing papers that cite at least five of the focal paper’s cited references. The DI_5 is equivalent to:

$$DI_5 = \frac{N_F - N_B^5}{N_F + N_B^5 + N_R}$$

3. Theory

Leibel and Bornmann (2024) provide an overview of the research on the DI_1 and its variants. Some previous studies tested whether disruption scores correspond to expert assessments of disruptiveness or related concepts (e.g., novelty). A possible disadvantage of this approach is that the criteria underlying the expert evaluations may remain unknown. In our study thus, we took advantage of survey data in order to investigate how researchers define groundbreaking research. Following Polanyi (1962) and Weinberg (1963), we differentiate four dimensions of research quality: scientific importance, novelty/originality, societal impact and methodological solidity. We presumed that researchers consider these dimensions of research quality when deciding whether a FP can be considered groundbreaking or not. We expected that groundbreaking research is rated more highly on at least one dimension of research quality compared to standard research.

H1: Groundbreaking research is rated more highly than standard research on at least one of the four dimensions of research quality.

With the exception of Wang et al. (2023), previous validation studies found that the DI_1 and its variants are convergently valid with expert/peer judgments (Leibel & Bornmann, 2024). Given this recurring result in the literature, we expected to find similar results in our study.

H2a: The DI_1 is convergently valid with researchers’ self-assessments.

H2b: The DI_5 is convergently valid with researchers’ self-assessments.

However, the literature also provides evidence that supports a competing hypothesis. The DI_1 and its variants assign high disruption scores to papers that are often cited independently of their links to cited references. This seems to conflict with scholarly citation practices: “It is rare for a scholar to cite only one recent ‘new’ result, especially if it disputes rather than confirms previous work on the topic; it is hard to imagine such a paper moving through peer review successfully” (Leahey et al., 2023, p. 566). Furthermore, we can expect that research, even groundbreaking research, contradicting established findings or theories is a rare event. Wuestman et al. (2020) analyzed the contents of 335 articles that were included in *Science*

² We calculated N_R such that it only includes papers that were published in the same years as the FP publication or later.

magazine’s annual announcement of the “Breakthrough of the Year”. The authors uncovered two remarkable features of scientific breakthroughs: First, the vast majority of scientific breakthroughs (77% of 335 papers) are “driven by a known question that is in line with theory” (Wuestman et al., 2020, p. 1211). Second, only 11% of *Science* magazine’s “Breakthrough of the Year” articles question the state-of-the-art literature. Taken together with the example of Davis et al. (1995) about the Bose-Einstein condensation, it seems that many groundbreaking papers are no more disruptive than standard research (as defined by DI_1 and DI_5).

H2c: The average DI_1 and DI_5 scores of groundbreaking papers are not convergently valid with researchers’ self-assessments.

4. Methods

4.1 Study design and questionnaire

Table 1: Survey questions and answer alternatives

Question	Answer alternatives
How do you regard the <u>scientific importance</u> of the research reported in these articles (e.g. in terms of new discoveries/findings, theoretical developments, new analytic techniques)?	1 (low)–2–3–4–5 (high)- Cannot say/Not relevant
How do you regard the <u>novelty/originality</u> of the research reported in these articles (e.g. of in terms of topic addressed, research question, methodology, and results)?	
How do you regard the <u>solidity</u> of the research reported in these articles (i.e. validity and certainty/reliability of the methods and results reported)?	
As far as you know, has the research/results presented in these articles had any <u>societal impact</u> (i.e. effect on, change or benefit to the economy, society, culture, public policy or services, health, the environment or quality of life, beyond academia)?	Yes-No-Don’t Know
Would you consider your article as ‘groundbreaking research’?	
Please characterize the main contribution(s) from these articles (multiple answers possible)	Theoretical-Empirical- Methodological-Review- Cannot say/Not relevant

Our study relies on a combination of survey data and bibliometric data. The survey was conducted by Aksnes et al. (2023) and was sent out in January 2022 to a sample of 1,250 scientists affiliated with a Norwegian institution, of which 592 responded (response rate: 47%). The survey asked researchers to rate three of their own papers, selected by stratified random sampling, across four dimensions of research quality: scientific importance, novelty/originality, solidity, and societal impact (Table 1). In addition, the respondents were asked to state whether

they would consider the respective article as “groundbreaking research”. The survey also provides information about the publication type of a paper.

The respondents rated the quality of their publications on a scale from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest). Since only few researchers gave their own work a rating of “1” or “2” on any of the quality dimensions, we binarily recoded the answer so that the ratings “1”, “2”, and “3” are coded as “low” and the rating “4” and “5” are coded as “high”.

Our study design takes advantage of the multi-level structure of our data: Since each respondent assessed multiple papers, we calculated fixed effect regressions. Standard ordinary least squares and logistic regression models suffer from omitted variables bias if there is person-specific unobserved heterogeneity. For example, some researchers might have a more favourable opinion of their own work than others. Fixed effect regressions are less susceptible to omitted variable bias because they wipe out all person-specific unobserved heterogeneity (Allison, 2009; Brüderl & Ludwig, 2015).

4.2 Sample description

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Variable	<i>n</i>	Min	Max	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Publication year	1,398	2,015	2,018	2,016.597	1.103
Number of linked cited references	1,398	10	157	34.699	18.193
Number of missing cited references	1,398	0	131	13.683	13.152
DI ₁	1,398	-14.39	16.13	-0.390	1.110
DI ₅	1,398	-9.51	28.57	0.101	1.224
Groundbreaking research	1,354	0	1	0.278	
Scientific importance	1,346	0	1	0.694	
Novelty/Originality	1,364	0	1	0.263	
Solidity	1,365	0	1	0.736	
Societal impact	1,341	0	1	0.871	

The original sample consisted of 1,776 papers, which were assessed by 592 respondents. We restricted the sample using the following three steps: 1) We deleted papers for which we could not retrieve bibliometric data because the FP is not indexed in the Web of Science (WoS, Clarivate). 2) We removed papers with the document type “review”. Reviews are consolidating by nature, but they may receive high disruption scores if they are often cited independently of their cited references. 3) Because the WoS does not offer complete coverage of the entire science system, we differentiate between two types of cited references: *Linked* references are indexed in the WoS and *missing* references are not indexed in the WoS as source items. Aksnes and Sivertsen (2019) found that Norwegian research publications belonging to the social sciences and humanities are generally less well covered in the WoS, which leads to substantial amounts of missing data. Missing references are not considered in the calculation of the DI₁ and the DI₅. The literature on the disruption indices shows that missing data about a FP’s cited references and citing papers may lead to inflated and misleading disruption scores (Liang et al.,

2022; Ruan et al., 2021). Therefore, we excluded papers with less than 10 cited references that are indexed as source items. The final sample consists of 1,398 publications.

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for all variables that are of relevance for our study. To avoid small decimal places and improve the readability of tables, we multiplied the DI_1 and DI_5 scores by 100. We used a citation window of five years for both the DI_1 and the DI_5 . To address the risk the disruption scores may be misleading due to missing data, we repeated our calculations in a more restrictive sample with a higher proportion of linked references. The robustness check only included publications with at least 10 linked references and 10 citations (within five years of publication). Additionally, at least 75% of all cited references need to be linked references. The robustness check is based on 551 publications.

5. Results

We performed logistic regressions to analyze how the scientific community defines groundbreaking research in terms of research quality. Table 3 (in the appendix) shows the results from a standard logistic regression and Table 4 (in the appendix) shows the results from the fixed effects logistic regression.³ In Figure 2, the estimates from both models are converted into logarithmized odds and displayed side by side to enable a visual comparison of the results.⁴ The estimates from the fixed effects logistic regression are larger and have large confidence intervals because this model discards a lot of data: It considers only those authors with at least one standard publication and at least one groundbreaking publication. In both models, scientific importance and novelty/originality are more strongly associated with groundbreaking research than solidity and societal impact. In Figure 3, we converted the estimates from the standard logistic regression model into predicted probabilities. We found that the probability that a paper is considered as groundbreaking increases substantially if the respective papers receive a high rating on both “scientific importance” and “novelty/originality”. This result is in line with H1 and tells us that, in the eyes of the scientific community, groundbreaking research combines aspects of novelty with scientific importance.

Figure 2: Coefficient plot – Log. odds from multivariate logistic regression models with and without fixed effects. Coefficients show the increase in the logarithmized odds that a paper is considered as groundbreaking compared to the reference category

³ Note that Table 4 shows odds ratios, whereas Table 3 shows average discrete changes.

⁴ The figures in Section 5 were created in Stata with the graphic schemes provided by Bischof (2017) and the *coefplot* command provided by Jann (2014).

Figure 3: Predicted probability that a paper is considered as groundbreaking research depending on scientific importance and novelty/originality

Figure 4: Coefficient plot – Results from eight fixed effects regressions of “groundbreaking research” on DI₁ and DI₅ scores. The coefficients indicate whether the average disruption scores of groundbreaking research are higher or lower than the average disruption scores of standard research

In order to test H2a, H2b, and H2c, we calculated multivariate fixed effects regression models to see if groundbreaking research is associated with higher DI₁ and DI₅ scores than standard research. The results of the main analysis and the robustness check are displayed in Table 5 and Table 6 (in the appendix). Figure 4 shows the coefficients and confidence intervals from the bivariate and multivariate models as well as the results from the robustness check. The focus is on the sign and the size of the coefficients from the multivariate models. We find that the DI₅ shows a higher degree of convergent validity with researchers’ self-assessments than the DI₁.

This result is in line with findings from previous research (Bittmann et al., 2022; Bornmann et al., 2020; Bornmann & Tekles, 2021; Deng & Zeng, 2023). However, all models predict a statistically significant negative association between groundbreaking research and DI_1 scores. In the main analysis (multivariate), the disruption scores (multiplied by 100) of groundbreaking research are about -0.25 points lower on average than the DI_1 scores of standard research. The positive (but statistically insignificant) association between DI_5 scores and groundbreaking research does not hold in the robustness check. More importantly, the coefficients of DI_5 scores on groundbreaking research are consistently small (and possibly negligible) across all models. None of the models we tested predicts a robust and relevant positive association between disruption scores and the self-assessments of researchers. Overall, this result favours H2c over H2a and H2b. It seems that one cannot expect high disruption scores if research has been characterized as groundbreaking by researchers.

6. Conclusion

Funk and Owen-Smith (2017) and Wu et al. (2019) convincingly argue that measures of citation impact fail to capture certain key features of technological and epistemic innovations. The fact that a paper is highly cited does not tell us whether it consolidates or disrupts the status quo. In this paper, we argue that the converse may also be true: The fact that a paper has been identified as disruptive (or not) does not tell us much about the importance of its contribution to scientific progress (measured in terms of bibliometrics). Our findings show that publications, which have been assessed by researchers as groundbreaking and important and original contributions to their respective fields, are on average no more disruptive than standard publications (as measured by the metrics). Our findings suggest that even if papers and patents are attesting less disruptiveness over time (Park et al., 2023), this may not necessarily entail that we are experiencing a decline of major scientific achievements. However, the significance of our study may be limited by the fact that we considered only a small sample of researchers who are affiliated with an institution in only one country.

Appendix

Table 3: Average discrete changes from a multivariate logistic regression of four dimensions of research quality on “groundbreaking research”

Effect	ADC	SE	95% CI		p
			LL	UL	
Scientific importance					
Low	Reference				
High	0.28	0.023	0.23	0.32	< .001
Novelty/Originality					
Low	Reference				
High	0.28	0.021	0.24	0.32	< .001
Solidity					
Low	Reference				
High	0.08	0.046	-0.01	0.17	0.067
Societal impact					
No	Reference				
Yes	0.07	0.026	0.01	0.12	0.011
<hr/>					
<i>Pseudo R²</i>	0.22				
<i>n</i>	1,307				

Note. ADC = average discrete change (in the predicted probability that a paper is considered as groundbreaking); SE = standard error; CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit

Table 4: Odds ratios from a multivariate fixed effects logistic regression of four dimensions of research quality on “groundbreaking research”

Effect	OR	SE	95% CI		p
			LL	UL	
Scientific importance					
Low	Reference				
High	37.79	33.81	6.54	218.29	< .001
Novelty/Originality					
Low	Reference				
High	55.96	50.25	9.63	325.30	< .001
Solidity					
Low	Reference				
High	4.78	3.13	1.32	17.27	0.017
Societal impact					
No	Reference				
Yes	4.08	1.55	1.93	8.59	< .001
<i>n</i>	590				

Note. OR = odds ratio; SE = standard error; CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit

The sample was restricted to papers from authors with at least one groundbreaking publication and at least one standard publication.

Table 5: Results from two separate fixed effects regressions of “groundbreaking research” on DI₁ scores and DI₅ scores.

Effect	DI ₁			DI ₅		
	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>
Groundbreaking research						
No	Reference			Reference		
Yes	-0.25	0.12	0.033	0.15	0.13	0.258
Publication type						
Theoretical	Reference			Reference		
Empirical	-0.30	0.19	0.119	-0.24	0.14	0.104
Methodological	0.15	0.30	0.607	0.28	0.37	0.442
Multiple	-0.53	0.30	0.078	-0.54	0.30	0.075
Discipline						
Health	Reference			Reference		
Humanities	0.18	0.29	0.531	0.19	0.19	0.319
Medicine	0.03	0.13	0.785	-0.09	0.17	0.593
Natural sciences	0.10	0.14	0.499	-0.08	0.14	0.548
Social sciences	0.36	0.26	0.165	0.02	0.12	0.885
Technology	0.40	0.32	0.214	0.57	0.37	0.122
Publication year						
2015	Reference			Reference		
2016	0.17	0.11	0.110	0.00	0.11	0.994
2017	0.12	0.10	0.233	0.09	0.13	0.460
2018	0.19	0.11	0.091	0.10	0.10	0.336
Log. number of linked references	-0.20	0.12	0.092	-0.60	0.16	< .001
Constant	0.39	0.45	0.388	2.29	0.54	< .001
<i>R</i> ²	0.05			0.07		
<i>n</i>	1,340			1,340		

Note. CI = confidence interval; SE = standard error.

The sample was restricted to papers with at least 10 linked references.

Table 6: Robustness check. Results from two separate fixed effects regressions of “groundbreaking research” on DI₁ scores and DI₅ scores.

Effect	DI ₁			DI ₅		
	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>	Estimate	SE	<i>p</i>
Groundbreaking research						
No	Reference			Reference		
Yes	-0.52	0.15	0.001	-0.12	0.07	0.093
Publication type						
Theoretical	Reference			Reference		
Empirical	-0.23	0.33	0.493	-0.26	0.24	0.274
Methodological	-0.09	0.40	0.824	-0.42	0.32	0.188
Multiple	-0.27	0.32	0.400	-0.28	0.22	0.209
Discipline						
Health	Reference			Reference		
Humanities	0.28	0.41	0.489	0.09	0.11	0.423
Medicine	0.51	0.30	0.084	-0.01	0.11	0.904
Natural sciences	0.35	0.38	0.360	-0.04	0.16	0.805
Social sciences	3.95	1.86	0.035	0.38	0.49	0.443
Technology	0.56	0.77	0.469	0.44	0.32	0.170
Publication year						
2015	Reference			Reference		
2016	-0.08	0.14	0.577	-0.10	0.08	0.206
2017	-0.27	0.20	0.183	-0.07	0.09	0.447
2018	-0.01	0.13	0.921	0.09	0.07	0.169
Log. number of linked references	0.42	0.20	0.033	-0.18	0.11	0.095
Constant	-2.16	0.91	0.019	0.89	0.52	0.090
R^2	0.20			0.10		
<i>n</i>	551			551		

Note. CI = confidence interval; SE = standard error.

The sample was restricted to FPs with at least 10 linked references and at least 10 citations (within 5 years of publication). Additionally, at least 75% of the FP’s cited references need to be linked references.

Competing interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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Open Science practices

Data are not available. The participants of this study did not give written consent for their data to be shared publicly. Bibliographic record data cannot be released due to copyright/license restrictions.

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